

Synthesis of 3'-[4-Aryl-2-thiazolyl]-6'-aryl-imidazo[2,1-*b*]thiazoles as Possible Antibacterials

M N IOSHI[†], V S BHAGWAT and I A PARVAII.

Chemistry Department, Parle College, Dixit Road, Vile Parle (East), Bombay-400 057

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(2,4'-Bithiazole)-2'-amine-4-aryl are potent anti-inflammatory agents¹. Imidazo[2,1-*b*]thiazoles are reported to possess fungicidal and antihistaminic activities². Literature survey reveals that no imidazo[2,1-*b*]thiazoles have been reported starting from 2,4'-bithiazole moiety. In continuation of our work, it was therefore thought of interest to synthesise new imidazo[2,1-*b*]thiazoles (Scheme 1) and evaluate their antibacterial activity.

Compounds **3** were tested for antibacterial activity against *E. coli*, *S. abony*, *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa* using cup-plate method in acetone medium (0.5% concentration) and the activity was compared with furazolidone³ as standard. Compounds **3** were much less active against *E. coli* (zone of inhibition ~14 mm; furazolidone ~35 mm) and *S. abony* (~14 mm; furazolidone ~31 mm), less active against *S. aureus* (~14 mm; furazolidone ~20 mm), but more active against *P. aeruginosa* (~14 mm; furazolidone ~12 mm).

Experimental

All m.p.s. were recorded in open capillary and are uncorrected. Purity of compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 781 spectrophotometer, mass spectra on an AEI MS 902 spectrometer and nmr spectra on a FT-NMR (80 MHz) instrument.

(2,4'-Bithiazole)-2'-amine-4-aryl¹ (**1**) and *o*-bromoacetophenones¹ were synthesised by known methods.

2'-Imino-3'-phenacyl-4'-[4-aryl-2-thiazolyl] -thiazolium bromide (**2**): A mixture of **1** (0.01 mol) and *o*-bromoacetophenone (0.01 mol) in dry benzene (30 ml) was kept at room temperature for 48 h, when the products 2'-imino-3'-phenacyl-4'-[4-aryl-2-thiazolyl]-thiazolium bromide (**2**) separated out as crystalline solids (60–70%): **2a**, m.p. > 270⁰; **b**, > 270⁰; **c**, 243⁰; **d**, 249⁰; **e**, > 270⁰; **f**, 242⁰; **g**, > 270⁰; **h**,

257⁰; **i**, 250⁰; **j** > 270⁰; **k**, 261⁰; **l**, 263⁰; **m**, 249⁰; **n**, 260⁰; **o** > 270⁰; **p**, > 270⁰; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) **3** 120 (NH), 1 710 (C=O) and 1 610 cm⁻¹ (C=N).

a: X = Y = H	i: X = CH ₃ , Y = H
b: X = H, Y = Cl	j: X = CH ₃ , Y = Cl
c: X = H, Y = CH ₃	k: X = Y = CH ₃
d: X = H, Y = OCH ₃	l: X = CH ₃ , Y = OCH ₃
e: X = Cl, Y = H	m: X = OCH ₃ , Y = H
f: X = Y = Cl	n: X = OCH ₃ , Y = Cl
g: X = Cl, Y = CH ₃	o: X = OCH ₃ , Y = CH ₃
h: X = Cl, Y = OCH ₃	p: X = Y = OCH ₃

Scheme 1

3'-[4-Aryl-2-thiazolyl]-6'-aryl-imidazo[2,1-*b*]thiazole (**3**): Method 1: A mixture of **1** (0.01 mol) and *o*-bromoacetophenone (0.01 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for 7 h. The contents were then cooled and poured over ice-water and basified with liquor ammonia. The resulting solid was washed with water, dried and crystallised from benzene-acetone (1 : 1) to yield the products (60–70%).

Method 2 : Compound **2** (0.01 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for 6 h. The contents were then cooled, poured over ice-water and basified with liquor ammonia. The resulting solid was washed with water, dried and crystallised from benzene-acetone to yield the products (50–65%) : **3a**, m.p. 206^o, *m/z* 359 (*M*⁺), 255, 217, 134, 103, 83, 77 and 68; **3b**, 218^o; **c**, 215^o, δ (80 MHz; CDCl₃) 2.54 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.12–7.82 (12H, m, Ar, thiazole, imidazole); **d**, 210^o; **e**, 243^o; **f**, 231^o; **g**, 230^o; **h**, 235^o; **i**, 236^o; **j**, 215^o; **k**, 225^o; **l**, 221^o; **m**, 227^o; **n**, 234^o; **o**, 237^o; **p**, 239^o, $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 600 cm⁻¹ (C=N).

References

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